

ISic2735

I.Sicily inscription 2735

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

building; honorific
(?)

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

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Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Segesta

Place of origin (modern)

Segesta

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Segesta, excavation stores, inventory SG5192

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Σ[---]

Apparatus

Text of Ampolo and Erdas; Nenci 1995:

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644835

PHI 333222

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 45.1400

Nenci, G. 1995. Iscrizioni greche e latine. *Annali della scuola normale superiore di Pisa*. ser.3, vol.25: 1182-1187. At 1184 no.9

Ampolo, Carmine, Erdas, Donatella 2019. *Inscriptiones Segestanae. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Segesta*. Pisa. At G29

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic2735. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4355015>